

reaction series is thought to be significant. This approach has already been used with varying degree of success in the field of NMR⁴ & IR⁵; and recently, correlations with visible spectra have also been reported⁶⁻⁷. It was, therefore, decided to examine the spectra of azo-rhodanines bearing different types of polar substituents at the azo-moiety in II. Thus starting from 3-benzylrhodanine and using a series of *para*- and *meta*-substituted anilines, a number of compounds (II; R=CH₂Ph) were prepared as recorded in Table-I; other physico-chemical properties are summarised in Table II, and representative absorption curves are shown in figs. 1 and 2.

FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Azorhodanines in methanol.

FIG. 2

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of Azorhodanines in chloroform.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TLC: Azo-compounds are known⁸ to exist both in the *cis*- and *trans*-forms, and the predominance of one form over the other is a function of the thermodynamic parameters. Nevertheless, each form, when pure, is discernible by its distinct absorption spectra and that due to the *trans*-form is usually more intense over the other. Hence, apart from chemical purity, stereo-chemical homogeneity of the prepared compounds is also desirable for deducing reliable conclusions.

To the extent that surface adsorption is controlled, at least in part, by the geometry of the molecule⁹, the samples were submitted to *TLC* with a variety of solvents, but in each case single spot was obtained with each compound and typical *R_f* values with two different solvent systems are shown in Table I. It thus appears that the compounds are essentially homogeneous and the only distinguishing mark is relatively lower *R_f* values for compounds bearing hydroxyl groups.

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TABLE I

Physico-chemical data of Azo-rhodamines (II).

Sl. No.	R=CH ₂ Ph R' =	M.P., °C	Rf		Mol Formul.	Analysis			
			Solv. A	Solv. B		Found%		Reqd %	
						C	H	C	H
1.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	192 ^a	0.52	0.75	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS ₂	59.70	4.42	59.81	4.40
2.	<i>p</i> -OH	240 ^b dec.	0.16	0.40	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	56.33	3.88	55.98	3.79
3.	<i>m</i> -OH	243 ^a dec.	0.25	0.51	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	55.85	3.95	55.98	3.79
4.	<i>p</i> -OMe	170 ^a	0.36	0.68	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	57.02	4.02	57.14	4.20
5.	<i>p</i> -OEt	167 ^a	0.47	0.66	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	57.82	4.48	58.22	4.58
6.	<i>p</i> -Cl	180 ^a	0.52	0.77	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ OS ₂	52.87	3.46	53.11	3.32
7.	<i>m</i> -Cl	186-7 ^a	0.50	0.67	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ OS ₂	53.29	3.45	53.11	3.32
8.	<i>p</i> -Br	182-3 ^c	0.52	0.75	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ OS ₂	47.32	3.00	47.30	2.96
9.	<i>p</i> -I	175 ^a	0.48	0.72	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ IN ₃ OS ₂	42.25	2.51	42.38	2.65
10.	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ NH ₂	132-3	0.06	0.41	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S ₃ 0.5H ₂ O	45.86	4.05	46.26	3.37
11.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	210-12 ^a	0.43	0.69	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	52.03	3.65	51.62	3.23
12.	<i>p</i> -CO ₂ H	267 ^a dec.	0	0.25	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂ .H ₂ O	52.82	3.83	52.44	3.85

Cryst. Solvts. (a) methanol-acetone, (b) acetone, (c) methanol. TIC Solvts. (A) Hexane (b.p., 67-69°) (75): ethyl acetate (25), v/v, (B) Benzene (80): methanol (20), v/v.

IR Spectra: IR spectra for similar type of compounds have been recorded earlier^{2a}. For the series of compounds recorded here, only the *p*-ethoxy-derivative (No. 6, Table II) was chosen at random as a representative member of the series. As before^{2a}, there was no indication of any band corresponding to >N-H, but the presence of other prominent bands, as noted below, allow us to assign azo-structure(II) for the diazo-coupling products; i.r. spectrum (KBr disc), ν max 1715 (C=O)¹⁰, 1538 (-N=N-), 1495 (=N—C=S) cm⁻¹.

UV Spectra: The results of UV measurements are given in Table II. In general two bands of nearly equal intensities appear around 240 m μ and 295-300 m μ region as shown in fig.1. The low wavelength band seems to be affected by the type of the polar substituents in the 5-aryldazo group, but the other band, by and large, remains unaffected, and it appears to be a composite one.

Of the two bands in the UV region, 240 m μ band is usually attributed to S transition¹¹. And this assignment is basically correct, otherwise, it is difficult to explain the observed effect of azo-chromophore on the 240 m μ band. Hence the observed effect of strongly polar group could be fairly understood by imposing some restriction on the delocalisation of S electrons at the transition stage. Inspection of results in Table II indeed suggests a small but discrete change in transition probability (hence red shift) with increase in Hammett σ values. Indeed in the case of *p*-nitro compound, the low wavelength band appears only as inflexion around 250 m μ . Further, the drift manifests itself in the Hammett plot as shown in fig. 3; but considerable scattering of the points does not allow

10. F. C. Brown *et al*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 1056.

11. (a) M. J. Janssen, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1960, **79**, 454, 464.

(b) P. B. Talukdar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 17.

any satisfactory calculation of correlation coefficient. However, the most significant point is the reversed sign of ρ indicating the opposing effect of azo-chromophore on the delocalisation of S electrons.

Briefly, the presence of an aryl-azo group at C₅ in I appears to exert an electron withdrawing influence on S-transition; and our previous observations^{2a} along with those recorded here may therefore be understood in terms of this effect, As a logical extension of this concept, the Hammett σ constant for an unsubstituted phenylazo group should be positive; and the reported¹² σ value (+0.640) for an unsubstituted phenylazo residue is in accord with our results.

FIG. 3

Fig. 3. Plots of $10^3/\lambda_{\max}$ vs Hammett σ values as determined in methanol. Solid circles indicate UV data. Numbers correspond to compounds in Table II.

FIG. 4

Fig. 4. Plots of $10^3/\lambda_{\max}$ vs Hammett σ values as determined in chloroform solution. Numbers correspond to compounds in Table II.

Visible Spectra: Typical absorption curves for a few compounds are shown in figs. 1 & 2. It is clear that the dyes usually exhibit a symmetrical maxima both in chloroform and in methanol. The observed $\lambda_{\max}$ was therefore directly used in ascertaining the substituent effect. Indeed the plots of $\lambda_{\max}$ or $10^3/\lambda_{\max}$ (which is directly proportional to transition energy) vs. σ indicated smooth dependence of data on Hammett σ constants as shown in figs. 3 & 4; and the corresponding data for all the compounds are summarised in Table II. Except for the *p*-nitro compound all other points fall fairly close along a straight line with slopes equal to 0.247 & 0.242 in chloroform and methanol respectively, and the corresponding equations for straight lines were found to be $10^3/\lambda_{\max} = 2.303 + \sigma \times 0.247 (\pm 0.0044)$ and $2.324 + \sigma \times 0.242 (\pm 0.0079)$ in chloroform and methanol respectively excluding the *p*-Me and *p*-NO₂ derivatives.

The fact that there is excellent correlation between $1/\lambda_{\max}$ and σ suggests that the substituents exert pronounced electronic effect at the excited state of the molecule. Since Hammett σ constants reflect nullifying compromise between opposing inductive and resonance effects, the observed effect therefore must be due to both inductive and resonance effects. In any event, the net effect would be lowering of transition energy causing absorption to occur at a longer wavelength with a powerful electron donor at the *para* position. This is corroborated by the occurrence of $\lambda_{\max}$ around 425 m μ for most of the *para*-substituted compounds and at 450 m μ for the strongly electron donating *p*-ethoxy compound.

In methanol solution $\lambda_{\max}$ for all the compounds tend to be shifted to lower wavelength ($\sim 6-8 \text{ m}\mu$). This blue shift is evidently due to solvent-solute interaction leading to stabilisation of the ground state by solvation. This kind of solvent induced blue shift is a well-known phenomenon and has already been investigated by many workers^{13,14}. In the present instance, the energy difference as calculated from the difference in $\lambda_{\max}$ (visible) was found to be in the order of 1 Kcal/mole.

TABLE II
Spectral data of Azo-rhodanines (II).

Sl. No.	R=CH ₂ Ph R'= in II	Hammett Constants (σ) ^a	Visible				UV	
			CHCl ₃ $\lambda_{\max}$ (m μ)	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$	MeOH $\lambda_{\max}$ (m μ)	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$	MeOH $\lambda_{\max}$ (m μ)	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$
1.	H	O	416	29.9	—	—	—	—
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-0.170	428	28.0	430	29.9	242 265 295	9.4 6.7 10.9
3.	<i>p</i> -OH	-0.370	452-56* (444)	26.8	446-48	26.6	240 296-97	9.2 11.7
4.	<i>m</i> -OH	+0.121	426-28* (426)	25.1	424-26	25.9	297	9.8
5.	<i>p</i> -OMe	-0.268	440-42	26.3	442-44	25.5	237-38 296-97	9.0 10.9
6.	<i>p</i> -OEt	-0.250	450	26.0	442	24.0	238 296	9.0 10.4
7.	<i>p</i> -Cl	+0.227	424	31.0	416-18	29.0	244 292-95	10.7 10.8
8.	<i>m</i> -Cl	+0.373	416	29.8	410	29.4	241-42 292-95	10.0 10.3
9.	<i>p</i> -Br	+0.232	424	30.8	418	30.3	243 295	11.1 11.4
10.	<i>p</i> -I	+0.276	422	31.6	424	31.6	245 296-98	13.5 11.6
11.	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ NH ₂	+0.570	414	29.8	410	31.1	249 294-96	10.4 10.9
12.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	+0.778	426* (418) sh 560* 595*	30.0 25.0 39.1	420-22 540-45	31.9 7.6	250 —	7.8 —
13.	<i>p</i> -CO ₂ H	+0.406	418* 530*	26.5 16.0	422 460	34.9 22.8	258 299-300	10.9 13.2

a: Data taken from 'Reaction Rate Methods' by H. B. Mark *et al.* in 'Advances in Analytical Chemistry & Instrumentation', Vol. 2., C. N. Reilly, Ed., Interscience Publishers, New York, N. Y., 1965, p.318.

*In acetone solvent. sh=shoulder.

13. V. G. Krishna and L. Goodman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2042,
M. Ito, K. Innzuka and S. Iminishi, *ibid*, 1960, **82**, 1317.
14. E. W. Crandall and J. Olguin, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 972.

The behaviour of the *p*-nitro compound with two peaks in the visible region could be understood in terms of resonating charged structure in equilibrium with the uncharged structure. In the former case, the conjugated system would be effectively extended, hence $\lambda_{\max}$ is expected to appear at a higher wavelength region in comparison to that of an uncharged structure; thus the 595 $m\mu$ band must be associated with the charged structures and the 418 $m\mu$ band (chloroform) or 426 $m\mu$ band (acetone) is due to the uncharged form.

Moreover, the extinction coefficient is proportional to the square of the dipole moment in going from ground state to the excited state, so an increase in the distance of charge separation will be reflected in a higher extinction coefficient (ϵ). This indeed was found to be the case for $\lambda_{\max}$ at 595 $m\mu$ in chloroform; but the stabilising effect of solvation (in methanol) on the ground state for the charged structures is reflected by the occurrence of a significant blue-shift with concomitant fall in the value of ϵ (see Table II).

With similar type of reasoning, the occurrence of two bands for the *p*-carboxy compound could be attributed to the undissociated form ($\lambda_{\max}$, 418 $m\mu$) and the resonating ion ($\lambda_{\max}$, 530 $m\mu$). However, in this instance, owing to the beneficial effect of a polar solvent (methanol) on dissociation, the 418 $m\mu$ band displays some redshift with increase in ϵ . On the other hand, the solvation of the charged structures in methanol causes, as before, considerable amount of blue shift, but the increased concentration of the charged species seems to overcome the usual lowering of ϵ associated with a blue shift.

Finally, the Hammett plots (figs. 3 & 4) suggest that the *p*-CH₃ compound is somewhat out of tune (except, *p*-NO₂) from the rest of the members. It is difficult to explain the situation without invoking the hyperconjugative effect as proposed by Roberts and his co-workers¹⁵.

In this connection, it appears to be tempting to examine the geometry of the molecule around -N=N- band. The observed band intensities for $\lambda_{\max}$ (Table II) shows excellent agreement with reported¹⁶ $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of *trans*-azobenzene ($\lambda_{\max}$, 379 $m\mu$; ϵ , 22,000) and *trans*-N, N-dimethyl-*p*-phenyl-azobenzene ($\lambda_{\max}$, 410 $m\mu$; ϵ , 30,400) and other closely related compounds. The relatively weak $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ band seems to be wholly overlain in most of the compounds (see figs. 1 & 2) by the intense $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band. Further, as maximum effect could be exercised only through overlap of π -orbitals, all these azo-derivatives (II) of rhodanine (including those reported earlier^{2a}) are essentially in *trans*

15. J. R. Roberts, R. K. Webb and E. A. McElhill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 408.

16. Ref. 8, p. 316.

configuration (IV). Additional discriminating evidence against any possible *cis* orientation (as in V) is under scrutiny at the moment; particularly, the dyes are expected to be susceptible to study by nmr owing to the shielding effect of sulphur.

It is also pertinent to keep on record a few interesting properties of the azo-derivatives(II). The compounds appear to be highly stable in the solid state and do not show any detectable change after storing for a year at room temperature. They exhibit poor to moderate solubility in common organic solvents. But in all cases, as before^{2b}, reversible colour change, depending on the *pH* of the medium, could be discerned. However, under alkaline condition decomposition, due to ring fission, occurred at a fairly fast rate, but recovery of the original compound is possible after quick acidification of the alkaline solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

M.Ps. are uncorrected. TLC experiments were conducted with silica gel (National Chemical Laboratory, Poona), and the wet plates were activated at 120° for 1 hr.

UV and Visible spectra were measured with Hilger UVSpek in 1 cm. stoppered quartz cell. Owing to poor solubility of some of the compounds in chloroform, visible spectra in a few instances were taken in acetone solution as noted in Table II. IR spectra were obtained through the courtesy of Dr. M. V. George, I. I.T., Kanpur.

The compounds listed in Table I were prepared essentially by the same method as reported earlier², and a typical preparation is described below.

Preparation of 3-benzyl-5-(p-tolylazo-) rhodanine: A solution of 3-benzylrhodanine (1.12 g., 5m mole) in dimethyl formamide (10 ml.) was cooled to about 5° and the solution was made weakly alkaline (*pH* 8-9) by adding a few drops of aq. ammonia (25%). The diazotised solution of *p*-toluidine (0.54 g., 5 mmole) was then added dropwise with control of *pH* and temperature. The mixture was agitated all through the period of addition and agitation was continued for 30 min. more after completion of addition. (In some cases progressive addition of more solvent, ethanol (90%) or acetone, was necessary in order to arrest the formation of gummy material.)

The precipitated crystals were collected and thoroughly washed with water. The yield of the dry crude material was almost quantitative in all cases and reduced to 70-80% after one crystallisation. Analytical samples were obtained after several crystallisations from methanol or methanol-acetone mixture.

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